

COLLABORATIVE IMPLEMENTATION OF CONSUMABLE GOODS IN THE TECHNICAL VOCATIONAL STRAND: A BASIS FOR IMPROVING ANNUAL IMPROVEMENT PLAN EXECUTION

Arnulfo D. Dinero, Ed.D.

Division of Sultan Kudarat, Region XII, Philippines

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13899039>

ABSTRACT

This study examines the collaborative implementation of consumable goods in the Technical Vocational Livelihood (TVL) Strand to enhance the Annual Improvement Plan (AIP). It investigates stakeholder perceptions and support from school administrators, teachers, and students in the Division of Sultan Kudarat. Using purposive sampling, insights were gathered from administrators, teachers, and students in selected senior high schools offering Technical-Vocational Livelihood Education. Data were collected via structured questionnaires and analyzed through frequency counts, percentages, and the Kruskal-Wallis Test. The findings indicate strong overall support for consumable goods, with high ratings for quality and administrative responsiveness. However, discrepancies emerged between the perceptions of school administrators and students regarding support levels, highlighting the need for improved resource allocation and alignment of support systems to meet the needs of both teachers and students. The study underscores the impact of school size, geographical location, and years of implementing the TVL program on administrative decisions and resource distribution. While the commitment to the TVL program is evident, the misalignment in stakeholder perceptions indicates a necessity for enhanced communication and collaboration. Future research is recommended to explore these dynamics in various regions to improve the applicability of findings and support for effective TVL education.

Keywords: *Collaborative, Technical-Vocational Livelihood, Perceptions, Support, Alignment, Sultan Kudarat, Philippines*

INTRODUCTION

The effective implementation of consumable goods is essential for the success of technical-vocational programs in senior high schools. Consumable materials, ranging from tools and equipment to supplies, directly impact the hands-on learning experiences of students. To ensure these resources are adequately provided and used, the Annual Improvement Plan (AIP) serves as a guiding framework, aligning the needs of the program with available resources and institutional goals.

In Thailand, the government has recognized the importance of a tripartite system involving technical and vocational institutes, employers, and government agencies to enhance vocational education. This collaboration is crucial for addressing labor market needs and ensuring the relevance and effectiveness of vocational training (Mongkhonvanit, 2017). The Thai government's commitment is further evidenced by strategic plans to increase the skilled workforce, which includes substantial investments in educational resources and consumables essential for practical training (Chalapati et al., 2020). Establishing robust funding frameworks is vital for providing these consumables, underscoring their role as a cornerstone of effective hands-on training in vocational education (Setiyawami et al., 2020).

Integrating consumable goods into the Tech-Voc curriculum in the Philippines is crucial for enhancing employability and addressing industry needs. Career development learning significantly impacts students' skills in sectors like food preparation and service management, vital to the local economy (Salape et al., 2020). Incorporating lessons on food safety and ethical consumption helps students navigate issues like food fraud and adulteration, which are prevalent in the consumer market (Kowalska, 2018). High-quality educational resources and a focus on ethical dilemmas, such as secondhand goods and counterfeits, also improve students' engagement and decision-making skills (Kuswanto et al., 2021; Ackerman et al., 2016; Ackerman et al., 2014).

The Division of Sultan Kudarat is committed to achieving quality education. The Annual Improvement Plan (AIP) plays a vital role in generating the necessary finances to ensure that Senior High School students receive real-life training experiences. Beyond the teachers' competence, it is their responsibility to provide students with hands-on training and ensure they benefit from the programs designed for them, particularly those enrolled in Technical-Vocational Livelihood tracks.

Research Questions

The study aimed to assess the collaborative implementation of consumable goods in the Technical Vocational Strand as a basis for improving Annual Improvement Plan execution. The investigation addressed the following questions:

1. What is the school profile of respondents in terms of:
 - a. school size classification;
 - b. geographic setting; and
 - c. years of senior high school TVL implementation?

2. To what extent do key stakeholders support and perceive the purchase and use of consumable goods in TVL programs in terms of:
 - a. the school administration's support for teachers;
 - b. teachers' affirmation of the school administration's support;
 - c. students' perception of the school administration's support; and
 - d. students' perception of teachers' assistance?
 3. Is there a significant difference in the responses of key stakeholders regarding their support for and perceptions of the purchase and use of consumable goods in TVL programs?
-

METHODOLOGY

The sampling for this study involved a purposive selection of key stakeholders, including school administrators, teachers, and students, from selected senior high schools offering Technical-Vocational Livelihood (TVL) programs.

This approach ensured that participants possessed relevant insights and experiences related to the support and utilization of consumable goods in these programs. A combination of stratified sampling was used to capture diverse perspectives across different schools within the specified geographic area, enhancing the study's validity and relevance.

RESULTS

On the respondent of the study that 5 school heads came from mega schools, 2 from large schools, and 3 from small schools. In addition to the school heads, the survey also included 10 Technical Vocational Livelihood (TVL) teachers and 20 TVL students from schools of all sizes. On the Senior High School TVL implementation 3 school heads, 12 Technical Vocational Livelihood (TVL) teachers, and 34 TVL students are from urban areas, while 7 school heads, 18 TVL teachers, and 26 TVL students are from rural areas.

On the level of School Administration's Support for Teachers in the Purchase and Use of Consumable Goods in TVL Programs revealed as "strongly agree".

On the Level of Teachers' Affirmation of the School Administration's Support in the Purchase and Use of Consumable Goods in TVL Programs, the Level of Students' Perception of the School Administration's Support in the Purchase and Use of Consumable Goods in TVL Programs, and the Level of Students' Perception of Teachers' Assistance in Purchase and Use of Consumable Goods in TVL Programs, revealed as "agreed".

DISCUSSION

On the school size classification

The data shows that 5 school heads came from mega schools, 2 from large schools, and 3 from small schools. In addition to the school heads, the survey also included 10 Technical Vocational Livelihood (TVL) teachers and 20 TVL students from schools of all sizes.

On the Geographic Setting

The distribution of respondents based on their geographical location. On the figure, 3 school heads, 12 Technical Vocational Livelihood (TVL) teachers, and 34 TVL students are from urban areas, while 7 school heads, 18 TVL teachers, and 26 TVL students are from rural areas.

On the Years of Senior High School TVL Implementation.

Illustrates the respondents' distribution based on the number of years their schools have implemented the Senior High School (SHS) Technical Vocational Livelihood (TVL) program. Many of the schools started their TVL implementation in 2016, coinciding with the first year of the K to 12 programs. In this group, 9 school heads, 28 TVL teachers, and 48 TVL students provided significant data for the study.

There were also respondents from schools that started implementing the TVL program 5 to 6 years later, including 1 school head, 1 TVL teacher, and 3 TVL students. Similarly, a group of respondents came from schools that began TVL implementation 3 to 4 years after the initial rollout, which included 1 TVL teacher and 7 students. Additionally, there were participants from schools that have only been implementing the TVL program for 0 to 2 years, comprising 1 teacher and 7 students.

On the stakeholder's support and perceive the purchase and use of consumable goods in TVL programs in terms of the school administration's support for teachers, teachers' affirmation of the school administration's support, students' perception of the school administration's support; and students' perception of teachers' assistance.

Table 1. Summary table on the stakeholder's support

Indicators	Mean	Interpretation
School administration's support for teachers	3.31	Strongly Agree
Teachers' affirmation of the school administration's support	3.06	Agree
Students' perception of the school administration's support	3.06	Agree
Students' perception of teachers' assistance	3.05	Agree

The table shows that the stakeholders and perceive the purchase and use of consumable goods in TVL programs in term of school administrators support for teacher got the highest computed mean of 3.31 which interpreted as “Strongly Agree”. Whereas, teacher’s affirmation of the school administrators support and Student’s perception of the administrations support got the equal computed mean of 3.06 which interpreted as “Agree”, and Students perception of teachers assistance got the lowest computed mean of 3.05 which interpreted as “Agree”.

On the significant difference in the responses of key stakeholders regarding their support for and perceptions of the purchase and use of consumable goods in TVL programs

Table 2. Significant difference in the responses of key stakeholders regarding their support for and perceptions of the purchase and use of consumable goods in TVL programs

Group 1	Group 2	H-value	p-value	Interpretation
School Admin	TVL Teachers	3.212	0.073	No Significant
TVL Teachers	TVL Students	0.756	0.385	No Significant
School Admin	TVL Students	12.215	0.001	Significant

The results indicate that there is no significant difference in the level of support provided by school administration to TVL teachers, as evidenced by an H-value of 3.212 and a p-value of 0.073. This finding suggests that teachers generally feel supported by their school administrators in terms of receiving consumable goods necessary for their instructional activities. The positive acknowledgment of this support indicates that the efforts of school administrators are recognized and appreciated by the teachers, which is critical for fostering a collaborative educational environment. These results corroborate

the findings presented in Table 3, which highlighted the school administrators' commitment to providing the necessary resources for their TVL programs.

This consistency across the data underscores the importance of administrative support in ensuring the effective implementation of TVL programs and emphasizes the need for continued investment in resources that enhance teaching and learning outcomes.

Research shows that many teachers face challenges in preparing assessment materials and delivering effective feedback due to limited resources and space constraints in classrooms and shop rooms (Jr, 2023; Basal, 2022). This underscores the need for administrators to provide access to essential consumable goods, such as tools, materials, and equipment, crucial for practical training. Addressing these resource gaps enables teachers to create a more effective learning environment, enhancing the quality of vocational education.

Conclusions

The following conclusions are drawn based on the findings of the study.

The research results indicate strong support from school administrations for the Technical Vocational Livelihood (TVL) program, as perceived by both teachers and students. Overall, stakeholders agree that consumable goods and materials are provided effectively and efficiently, with high ratings for the quality of materials and the administration's responsiveness to needs, highlighting a collaborative effort in resource allocation and support within the TVL framework. The analysis of stakeholder responses regarding the support and perception of consumable goods in Technical Vocational Livelihood (TVL) programs reveals generally positive sentiments, with teachers feeling adequately supported by school administrations. However, a notable discrepancy exists between the perceptions of school administrators and students, indicating that while administrators believe they are providing sufficient resources, students do not fully feel this support, highlighting the need for improved communication and alignment of resources with student needs to enhance the overall effectiveness of the TVL program.

Recommendations

From the salient findings of this study and the conclusion reached, the following recommendations are presented:

1. Establish regular communication channels between school administrations, teachers, and students to facilitate feedback on resource needs and perceptions of support.
2. Conduct assessments to better understand the specific needs of students regarding consumable goods and materials.
3. Provide training for school administrators on the importance of responsive resource allocation and effective communication strategies.

4. Implement a systematic approach to monitor and evaluate the use of consumable goods within the TVL programs.
5. Encourage collaborative planning sessions involving school administrators, teachers, and students when designing resource allocation strategies for the TVL programs.
6. Continue to prioritize the procurement of high-quality consumable goods and materials for TVL programs.
7. Future researchers could conduct longitudinal studies to track changes in administrative support, resource allocation, and student perceptions over time.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The authors affirm that there are no conflicts of interest related to this study. Ethical approval was obtained before the commencement of the research, and informed consent was acquired from all respondents involved. No specific funding was received for this research from any public, commercial, or not-for-profit organizations. The data supporting the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Acknowledgments

The acknowledgment goes to the participants for their shared time and contribution to the researchers whose work has been referenced in this paper and most especially to Leodie D. Mones, PhD, and Engr. Limwell Telmo for their technical assistance in completing this paper. Their valuable insights and findings have substantially contributed to the analysis of this study.

REFERENCES

- Ackerman, D., & Hu, J. (2014). Assuring me that it is as 'good as new' just makes me think about how someone else used it: Consumer reaction toward secondhand goods from an information processing perspective. In *Advances in Information Systems and Technologies* (pp. 716-719). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-10951-0_265
- Ackerman, D., & Hu, J. (2016). Assuring me that it is as 'good as new' just makes me think about how someone else used it: Examining consumer reaction toward marketer-provided information about secondhand goods. *Journal of Consumer Behaviour*, 16(3), 233-241. <https://doi.org/10.1002/cb.1631>
- Basal, D. (2022). Instructional competencies of technology and livelihood education (tle) teachers: basis for a competency-based module. *International Journal of Research Publications*, 96(1). <https://doi.org/10.47119/ijrp100961320222948>
- Chalapati, N., & Chalapati, S. (2020). Building a skilled workforce: Public discourses on vocational education in Thailand. *International Journal for Research in Vocational Education and Training*, 7(1), 67-90. <https://doi.org/10.13152/ijrvet.7.1.4>

- Jr, F. (2023). Competencies, instructional skills, and challenges of teachers in implementing the technical-vocational and livelihood senior high school track. *International Journal of Membrane Science and Technology, 10*(2), 653-678. <https://doi.org/10.15379/ijmst.v10i2.1304>
- Kowalska, A. (2018). The study of the intersection between food fraud/adulteration and authenticity. *Acta Universitatis Agriculturae Et Silviculturae Mendelianae Brunensis*, 66(5), 1275-1286. <https://doi.org/10.11118/actaun201866051275>
- Kuswanto, K., & Anderson, I. (2021). Effect of service quality and motivation on the consumption behavior of students in the academic services. *International Journal of Evaluation and Research in Education (IJERE)*, 10(1), 86. <https://doi.org/10.11591/ijere.v10i1.20794>
- Mongkhonvanit, J. (2017). Thailand's dual education system: A way forward. *Higher Education Skills and Work-Based Learning*, 7(2), 155-167. <https://doi.org/10.1108/heswbl-09-2016-0067>
- Salape, R., & Cuevas, E. (2020). The link between career development learning and employability skills of senior high school students. *University of Mindanao International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 6(1), 56-64. <https://doi.org/10.55990/umimrj.v5i1.505>
- Setiyawami, S., & Rahardjo, T. (2020). The role of vocational education on the advancement of human development in Indonesia. <https://doi.org/10.2991/assehr.k.200620.079>